

Scientific and Structural Deficits in the Toxicological Evaluation of Pesticide Active Substances – Implications for Human Health Risk Assessment

Reflections after 30 years of regulatory toxicology

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This text was prepared after the author's retirement. The author currently holds no institutional functions, has no mandates, and maintains no contractual or organisational ties.

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Summary

This report examines the scientific reliability of the toxicological testing of pesticide active substances using animal studies, and the assessment methodology used for their approval in the EU and Switzerland. The focus is on methodological and structural shortcomings of the assessment procedure, as well as the robustness of the health-related conclusions derived from it.

The approval of an active substance in the EU relies heavily on the assessment by a single Member State selected by the companies, which prepares a draft assessment report for the EU. These national assessments differ in quality, yet are binding for the entire EU. Switzerland adopts European approval decisions – i.e., in practice, national assessments. There is no longer any possibility of an independent review of EU decisions. As a result, methodological shortcomings in testing and assessment practice as well as qualitative differences between national assessments take immediate effect in Switzerland and can no longer be corrected.

Companies submit the animal studies to the selected EU Member State in PDF format. This format effectively prevents in-depth statistical analyses by authorities. Passages from the company dossier may be incorporated into the authorities' assessments without being identified in detail. Together, these two aspects give companies a great deal of influence over the authorities' assessments.

A key methodological problem of the toxicological testing of pesticide active substances is that the studies are generally conducted only once. Because their results – both positive and negative findings – are therefore not confirmed through replication (a central standard of scientific quality assurance), conclusions are not robust even for the animal strain studied, let alone for humans. This is clearly confirmed by pharmaceutical testing: results from animal studies there very often prove to be only of limited relevance for humans. Biological differences and differences in living conditions between individuals, animal strains and animal species, as well as the absence of testing in humans – which is mandatory in pharmaceutical development – lead to considerable uncertainties in the health assessment of pesticide active substances.

Authorities often question the relevance of positive findings in animal studies for humans far more critically than negative findings. This unequal assessment practice depending on the type of finding is scientifically indefensible and leads to a systematic underestimation of the toxicity of pesticide active substances.

Companies are not required to publish the raw data from the studies. This prevents an independent review of the conclusions of companies and authorities. Given the substantial influence of companies on the assessment, this appears problematic. In addition, it hampers the development of testing methods that do not rely on animal experiments.

Publicly accessible raw data would allow broader scientific scrutiny. This, in turn, would increase pressure to improve a testing and assessment practice that has remained largely unchanged for decades.

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1 Regulatory and institutional framework in Switzerland

Ready-to-use plant protection products, also referred to as pesticides, consist of one or more active substances as well as co-formulants. For co-formulants see Section 22.

While plant protection products in the European Union (EU) are generally authorised at national level, the authorisation of active substances takes place at Union level.

In Switzerland, the Ordinance on the Placing on the Market of Plant Protection Products (Pflanzenschutzmittelverordnung, PSMV) regulates both the authorisation of active substances and of plant protection products (PSMV; SR 916.161). The PSMV was recently revised. Under the new provisions, Switzerland adopts all EU active substances without conducting its own health assessment and, upon application by companies, also plant protection products authorised in neighbouring countries.

In Switzerland, the Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (FSVO) is simultaneously responsible for drafting the PSMV, for the health assessment, and for authorisation decisions. This concentration of rule-making, scientific assessment and decision-making authority in a single agency carries the risk of institutional conflicts of interest.

2 Dependence on the EU process

The revisions to the PSMV are problematic because Swiss authorisation is now based entirely on the EU's testing process (European Food Safety Authority, 2025), whose methodological foundations are scientifically questionable. To understand this criticism, a brief description of the European active-substance approval procedure is required.

First, manufacturing companies conduct animal studies to determine which toxic effects their active substances cause at which doses. Table 1 lists the animal studies that typically have to be conducted. Based on these studies, companies compile extensive dossiers which, in addition to the raw data of the studies, also contain summaries and the companies' own interpretations of the health risks. These dossiers, comprising several thousand pages, are converted into PDF format. The companies then select an EU Member State which, on behalf of the entire EU, prepares a draft assessment report based on this company dossier.

3 In-depth evaluation is hardly possible

Only machine-readable data formats allow in-depth statistical analyses of raw data from animal studies; the PDF format prevents this. It is incomprehensible that the EU accepts this format. It creates the impression that the EU is not aiming to evaluate the raw data independently from the ground up.

In addition, according to the relevant EU guidance documents, passages from the company dossier may be copied directly into the authorities' draft assessment report without having to be identified as such (European Food Safety Authority, 2021). In the context of the barely analysable PDF format this practice is understandable, but it gives companies very substantial and non-transparent influence over the draft assessment report.

Under the lead of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), other Member States and the public can comment on these draft assessment reports. However, the public has no access to the raw data of

the studies. Independent scientific review of the quality of the companies' and authorities' conclusions is therefore excluded.

4 Waiving assessment in Switzerland

This procedure is also criticised by the European Parliament (European Parliament, 2019). In Switzerland, however, it is largely unknown that EU approvals are based on national assessments of varying quality, and that these in turn are based on unpublished raw data, whose in-depth analysis is made difficult or impossible by the PDF format. The German Umweltbundesamt has found that manufacturers, when choosing the assessing Member State, tend to prefer those that apply less stringent assessment standards (Umweltbundesamt, 2025).

In practice, the assessment of an EU country becomes binding for Switzerland.

Given responsibility for the health of the Swiss population, it is incomprehensible that Switzerland voluntarily deprives itself of the possibility, where necessary, to examine the scientific basis of European approval decisions.

5 Comparison with pharmaceutical testing

Authorities imply that plant protection products are very safe by pointing out that their active substances – similar to medicinal products – are among the most thoroughly tested substances (Kuster, 2025). Yet precisely this comparison raises fundamental doubts about the reliability of active-substance testing. Around 90% of medicinal products that were considered as safe and effective in animal experiments later fail in studies in humans, among other reasons because they are more toxic or less effective than expected (Marshall et al., 2023). Some medicines are only withdrawn after marketing authorisation due to unexpected effects.

The limited translatability of results from animal studies to humans has long been known and is a major problem for drug development (Bailey et al., 2014). It shows that the few animals in a study cannot reliably represent the enormous biological diversity and differences in sensitivity of billions of people to chemical substances (Pound et al., 2018).

This unreliable translatability is particularly problematic because the testing processes for medicinal products and pesticide active substances differ fundamentally. For medicines, animal studies serve as a kind of preliminary screen; the relevant testing before approval takes place in clinical studies in humans. Pesticide active substances, by contrast, are tested exclusively in animals. The translatability problem simply remains undetected here.

In addition, after plant protection products are placed on the market there is no systematic monitoring of toxic effects, as is required for medicines.

6 Underlying assumptions of health regulation

Health regulation of active substances is based on two assumptions: first, that a dose that is safe for all humans can be derived from animal studies, and second, that all effects above this dose can be detected in such studies.

Pharmaceutical testing shows that the validity of both assumptions is scientifically untenable. Certain biological processes are sufficiently similar across many living organisms that the damaging potential of an active substance may sometimes be detected – but only if the active substance damages exclusively such processes. Other processes differ substantially between species and even

between individuals of the same animal strain. It follows that effects in rats may be irrelevant to humans or – more seriously – may occur in humans without having been observed in animal studies. Because the mechanisms underlying most toxic effects of active substances remain largely understood, the pattern of effects in humans cannot be predicted reliably. Accordingly, even closely related animal species often show different patterns of effects (Wright et al., 2023), which further underlines the fundamental unreliability of extrapolation to humans (Weitekamp et al., 2025).

7 Methodological weaknesses of the animal studies

In addition to this limited translatability, a central methodological problem of animal studies lies in their scientifically inadequate design. Studies are conducted with a very limited number of animals, only a few dose groups are examined, and studies are usually performed only once per animal strain. By today's scientific quality standards, the results are therefore not even validated for the animal strain studied, which further aggravates the significance of the already limited translatability to humans.

8 Lack of replicability of study results

The replication of an experiment is central for the reliability of any conclusion based on it (National Academies of Sciences Engineering Medicine, 2019).

The lack of validation through replication of studies with active ingredients of plant protection products is particularly worrying against the background that many research results in numerous scientific disciplines have proven to be non-replicable (Anonymous, 2014). This represents an immense credibility problem for the sciences. The pharmacologist Peter Meier-Abt captured one of the causes of this replicability problem succinctly: “A single experiment is not an experiment” (Meier-Abt, 2015).

If studies with pesticide active substances were systematically replicated, the extent of the lack of replicability of results would become apparent. A few examples.

For the active substance glyphosate, which has been investigated for carcinogenicity in more than ten studies, some studies indicate carcinogenic potential, others do not (European Food Safety Authority et al., 2023).

The now banned active substance chlorothalonil caused kidney tumours in one rat strain, but not in another (European Food Safety Authority et al., 2018).

Such indications of a lack of replicability of study results can also be found for other active substances, both regarding the induction of cancer and of malformations.

There is therefore no reason to assume that the testing of plant protection product active substances would be exempt from the replicability problems of other sciences.

9 Unjustified extrapolation of study results to humans

Despite all these weaknesses, positive results (the active substance shows an effect) from animal studies conducted only once are scrutinised critically, whereas negative results (the active substance shows no effects) are translated uncritically to humans:

- If particularly severe effects such as cancer or malformations occur, the active substance is often questioned as the cause by referring to uncertainties in study results and by using scientifically questionable assessment methods. Such approaches were recently illustrated using the example of the WHO's active-substance assessments, which in this respect are very similar to those of the EU (Zarn et al., 2024).
- If severe effects are absent, however, it is assumed uncritically that they will also not occur in humans – yet without any reference to the uncertainties of the studies. Scientifically, such a far-reaching generalisation without analysing its uncertainty is untenable. Nevertheless, it forms the basis for consequential regulatory decisions.

It is not mentioned that the causes of the uncertainties partly do not lie in biology, but in the chosen study conditions and the lack of replication of studies – that is, in the testing methodology based on the relevant guidelines for which the authorities are responsible.

The different use of uncertainties as an argument, depending on whether severe effects were observed or not, is arbitrary. It favours active-substance approval in a scientifically untenable way and leads to a systematic underestimation of the toxicity of active substances.

10 Missing analysis of evidential strength

In science, conclusions should always be accompanied by an analysis of their limitations. Not so in active-substance testing. Regulatory assessments usually contain neither quantitative nor qualitative analyses of uncertainties – despite the lack of validation of results through study replication, limited statistical power, and despite the presumed unreliable translatability to humans.

These omissions, together with the lack of transparency due to non-publication of study results, create for the public and political decision-makers the impression of scientific reliability of far-reaching conclusions that factually does not exist.

11 Scientifically unsubstantiated safety factors

Despite all these uncertainties, authorities derive a supposedly safe dose for humans by simply dividing the dose determined in animal studies by a factor of 100. This so-called safety factor was introduced as early as 1949 and was scientifically not substantiated (Lehman et al., 1949). Later attempts at justification were partly based on untenable assumptions. Experimental validation of this safety factor would require that, for a statistically meaningful number of active substances, the same data available for animals were collected in a statistically meaningful number of humans. No such database exists. Consequently, this safety factor is not validated. Its validity for several billion people is contradicted by everyday laboratory experience. Even within animal studies, one can often observe considerable individual differences in sensitivity between animals, which can lie within the range of this safety factor.

12 Consequences for humans and wild animals

Active substances with unrecognised risks are very likely to be approved. Given the global annual application of several million tonnes of active substances, this is worrying (FAO, 2024). Entire generations of humans and animals may simultaneously be exposed to a multitude of such substances. Studies from various world regions – including recently from the canton of Valais in Switzerland (Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute, 2025) – confirm such multiple exposures.

For decades, numerous scientific publications have pointed to possible health consequences of these exposures (Burns et al., 2021;Gatto et al., 2021;Cavalier et al., 2023).

13 Inconsistent application of the precautionary principle

A more appropriate way of dealing with all these uncertainties would at least require consistent application of the precautionary principle, which is enshrined in EU law. Evidence for an association between an active substance and harmful effects should be treated as proof of causality. That this hardly happens is illustrated by the example of the chemically very similar active substances isopyrazam (European Food Safety Authority, 2012), sedaxane (European Food Safety Authority, 2013) and benzovindiflupyr (European Food Safety Authority, 2015). Isopyrazam and sedaxane were tested in long-term studies up to doses exceeding the lowest toxic dose identified in preliminary studies. Both induced uterine tumours. Benzovindiflupyr, by contrast, was tested in female animals only up to about half of this dose. Although even at this low dose a doubling of uterine tumours was observed, it was not classified as carcinogenic due to a lack of statistical significance. Given the close chemical relationship of the three substances and the increase in uterine tumours, there would be good reasons for such a classification or at least for replication the study. Doing neither is hardly compatible with the precautionary principle.

14 Ethical arguments

The call for methodologically better studies should not be equated directly with a call for more animal testing. If anything, animal studies should of course only be allowed if they meet the highest scientific standards.

Occasionally, demands for further studies are opposed with ethical arguments. Therefore, a few figures to put animal use in active-substance testing into perspective. For the testing of currently approved active substances, an estimated two million animals were used worldwide over the last 50 years. That is as many as are used in the EU over three months for various testing or research purposes (European Commission, 2024), or as many as are slaughtered in Switzerland in nine days (Proviande, 2025). One more comparison: Swiss fields may be home to around 20 million mice (Aschwanden et al., 2007), relatives of laboratory animals whose welfare is cited by authorities and companies as an argument against additional animal studies. These animals, together with many others, are exposed to plant protection products directly or via their food.

If one were to extrapolate these figures globally over several decades, the two million laboratory animals in active-substance studies would be negligible in numerical terms.

15 Inconsistent use of ethical arguments

If animal welfare were truly a priority concern of companies and authorities, at the very least as much knowledge as possible would be gained per study and per animal, and all study results would be published.

This is demonstrably not the case.

- According to the guidelines for most study types, not all animals must be fully examined after they are killed, for example not even in carcinogenicity studies (OECD, 2018b). This makes the already complex assessment of study results more difficult because it prevents a holistic picture of the toxicological profile of active substances. Paradoxically, the resulting

uncertainty in the data can then be used to question the active substance as the cause of effects.

- The physiology of an animal and the metabolism of active substances may change during pregnancy. Nevertheless, in developmental studies the dams that are killed before their fetuses are removed are not fully examined (OECD, 2018a). In addition, no data on the metabolism of active substances are collected in dams. As a result, insights into risks for pregnant individuals may be lost.
- The central task of toxicologists is to identify the dose that leads to effects (Borgert et al., 2021). The typical study design hinders precisely this core task. In most studies, the active substance to be tested is administered to animals in the feed, mixed into the feed at a constant concentration over the entire study duration. This is simple and cost-effective. However, the consequence of this route of administration is that animals receive up to fivefold higher doses at the beginning of a long-term study than towards the end (Zarn et al., 2013). This route of administration not only leads to varying doses over the lifespan of each individual, but also to large dose differences between individuals within the same group. This method introduces unnecessary uncertainty into the assessment of the dose–response relationship (Zarn et al., 2018).
- The majority of animal studies are conducted with genetically heterogeneous animal strains. Each study population is therefore composed of animals that may differ in sensitivity. The genetics of the animals are unknown to toxicologists, as are the resulting differences in sensitivity. Combined with group sizes that are small from a statistical perspective and with few dose groups, this reduces the probability of detecting effects as statistically significant at all. The resulting uncertainty in the data is then sometimes used again to question the active substance as the cause of effects.
- Chemicals are partly converted in the body into very many metabolites. Often it is individual metabolites, rather than the parent compound itself, that are responsible for toxicity. The pattern of metabolism can change over the course of life. Nevertheless, in the vast majority of cases the metabolism of pesticide active substances is tested only in a few young animals. As a result, there is no knowledge of which metabolites predominate at which life stage. This makes interpretation of toxicological findings considerably more difficult.

These shortcomings in study design have primarily economic reasons.

The evaluation of toxicological studies is complex enough due to biological variability that is largely uncontrollable. From a scientific perspective, it is difficult to understand that this situation is allowed to be further exacerbated by deficient study design. And it is ethically hardly defensible to expose animals in studies to toxic substances without striving for maximum insight.

16 Loss of critical distance

In addition to the scientific shortcomings, the assessment and approval processes also have an institutional and personnel problem that is rarely addressed. Many experts have never themselves conducted the type of animal studies submitted by industry. Experimental expertise is lacking. Many move directly from academia into authorities and adopt new roles and ways of thinking. Especially at the beginning, many strive to understand and appropriate the administrative jargon and established assessment logics. Psychologically understandably, they seek integration into the new professional community. In the process, intellectual autonomy can gradually be lost which would be central to truly critical scrutiny. This form of adaptation is incompatible with the scientific

responsibility of regulatory toxicologists and is dangerous because it does not question technical and systemic weaknesses, but reproduces them.

This are well-described institutional socialisation effects in expert committees (Sedlar et al., 2023).

17 Role understanding of regulatory toxicologists

Authorities focus strongly on the conformity of studies with testing guidelines. It is assumed that compliant animal studies are automatically informative. However, despite substantial scientific progress, the guidelines have hardly changed in key respects for decades.

Moreover, the testing and assessment of active substances is often treated as a routine task to be worked through schematically rather than as a research question. Yet, for the protection of health, a different attitude would be necessary. Toxicologists in authorities can fulfil this responsibility only if they strive to identify, in an extremely critical manner, all possible risks and uncertainties in the data. Often, however, an attitude can be observed of tending to interpret uncertainties in favour of the substance (Zarn et al., 2024). Given the strong influence of industry on regulatory assessments, this endangers health.

18 Confidentiality of study results

Allowing manufacturers to keep toxicological study results confidential not only prevents an independent review of the authorities' assessments, but also hinders the development of animal-free methods, which depend on animal data as a reference. In addition, these data would be extremely valuable for academic research in toxicology to investigate fundamental biological relationships.

Keeping the results of animal studies confidential gives companies no mutual competitive advantage, but protects common interests by keeping methodological weaknesses hidden.

19 Strong influence of industry

From the above considerations it is clear that industry's influence is large, that of authorities is limited, and the influence of independent science is virtually non-existent. Given high investments of CHF 200 to 300 million (Craig et al., 2019), companies have a strong interest in marketing their active substances with as few restrictions as possible, which is likely to influence how they interpret study results for the authorities.

20 Company risks versus health risks

A further structural problem is the unequal distribution of risks arising from approved active substances. Unlike medicines, the approval of a pesticide active substance with previously unrecognised toxicity entails low risks for manufacturers. Pesticide active substances are not tested in humans, and there is a lack of systematic monitoring of possible health effects after market introduction.

As a result, companies face hardly any immediate negative consequences, because an active substance as the cause of toxic effects – if at all – can usually only be demonstrated years or decades later. Humans and animals bear the health risk. This asymmetry creates no incentive to treat uncertainties conservatively. It allows uncertainties in toxicological studies to be interpreted rather in favour of approval.

21 Credibility needs transparency

Transparency is a prerequisite for scientific credibility, quality control and societal legitimacy (National Academies of Sciences Engineering Medicine, 2019). A fundamental revision of active-substance testing is hence required.

Already today, however, authorities should actively shape animal studies, accept study results only in machine-readable form, fully evaluate them independently, and publish their assessment reports for public comment – based on publicly available raw data. Conclusions on health risks should always be justified in the light of the limitations of animal studies.

The influence of companies should be restricted. They should be allowed to submit only raw data from animal studies, but not summaries or interpretations. These influence regulatory assessments and are partly incorporated unchanged into the authorities' assessment reports.

Implementing such improvements is politically demanding. A critical analysis of the existing testing procedure would call the safety of past approvals into question and would require publication of study results. Such dynamics can therefore only emerge if society and politics consistently demand full transparency.

22 Note on co-formulants

Ready-to-use plant protection products contain, in addition to the active substances, so-called co-formulants. These serve, among other purposes, to stabilise the formulation, improve distribution or uptake of the active substances. They may also be toxicologically relevant.

Co-formulants are tested far less systematically than active substances. Their toxicological properties, their toxicological interactions with each other and with active substances are scarcely characterised. Thus, an active-substance assessment – even if it were scientifically reliable – captures the health risk of plant protection products only incompletely. This further reinforces the described weaknesses of active-substance testing.

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Table 1: Toxicological studies that typically have to be submitted for the authorisation assessment of plant protection products

Species*	Study	Animals per group and sex	Groups	Duration (days)	Number of doses
Rat	Acute ADME	5	2	3	1
	Acute oral toxicity	5	4	14	1
	Acute oral neurotoxicity	5	2	14	1
	Subchronic ADME	5	4	14	14
	Developmental toxicity	25	4	21	15
	Subacute oral toxicity	5	4	28	28
	Subchronic dermal toxicity	10	4	90	90
	Subchronic inhalation toxicity	10	4	90	90
	Subchronic oral toxicity	10	4	90	90
	Subchronic oral neurotoxicity	10	4	90	90
	Fertility	25	4	126	126
	Chronic oral toxicity	50	4	712	712
Mouse	Mouse micronucleus test	5	2	2	1
	Subacute oral toxicity	5	4	28	28
	Subchronic oral toxicity	10	4	90	90
	Chronic oral toxicity	50	4	534	534
Rabbit	Eye irritation	3	2	3	1
	Developmental toxicity	25	4	21	15
Dog	Subacute oral toxicity	4	4	28	28
	Subchronic oral toxicity	4	4	90	90
	Chronic oral toxicity	4	4	356	356
Hamster	Skin irritation	3	3	3	1

* The species is prescribed, the strain is not

Not all studies always have to be submitted.

Some studies are conducted with two sexes.

Overall, approximately 1860 animals are used for the testing of one active substance. If the fetuses from the developmental toxicity studies and the offspring from the fertility studies are included, this number roughly doubles.